

plate assays, but the cerulenin-producing wild-type isolates did. Grain inocula of the mutants did not induce ShR lesions on 55-d-old TKM9 and IR50 plants in the greenhouse; the wild-type isolates did (Fig. 2). The No. 22 mutant did not

induce ShR on TKM9 and IR50 and did not affect grain yield (grains/panicle, infected grains/panicle, and 1,000-grain weight) in a field experiment. Wild-type No. 22 affected grain yield due to ShR induction.

These results indicate that cerulenin, the toxin produced by *S. oryzae*, may play a role in the pathogen's virulence in ShR induction in rice and in its interaction with other fungal pathogens of rice. ■

Integrated pest management—insects

Farmers' estimates of percent whiteheads (WH)

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We conducted a study to compare farmers' estimates with actual counts of WH caused by stem borers (SB) in 24 ricefields in Muñoz, Nueva Ecija, Philippines, in Nov 1992. Varieties planted were IR64, IR42, C-1, and Bengawan. We marked a 40- × 40-hill area in the middle of each field and asked farmers to estimate percent WH in the area. We then counted WH and total tillers in the area and computed percent damage. We recorded yield at harvest and highest yield obtained from the same field in previous seasons. Percent yield reduction was computed as yield divided by highest yield from previous seasons multiplied by 100.

All farmers attributed the unusually high WH count in their fields in 1992 wet season (WS) to late planting resulting from the delayed arrival of irrigation water. All ricefields sampled were

planted after 15 Aug. In previous seasons, they had been planted as early as June.

It was not clear how farmers estimated percent WH. A few counted damaged tillers and then divided by total tillers of one or two hills near the bunds. Others based their estimates on experience or intuition.

Farmers tended to overestimate by 5-44%. Seventy-five percent overestimated by more than 5%, and almost 30% of these overestimated by 20-30%. Only two farmers underestimated (see figure). A *t*-test comparison between estimates and actual percentages showed that estimates differed significantly from actual percent damage by a mean difference of 13% (SE = 2.77).

Overestimates can influence farmers' decisions in applying controls. Some admitted applying insecticides after seeing WH, although it is too late to spray for SB when damage is evident.

Farmers equated percent WH to percent yield reduction. They all expected about the same reduction in yield as the WH estimate they had given. An estimate of

30% WH meant the farmer was expecting a yield loss of 30% compared with a season without SB damage. Farmers' estimates compared with actual yield reductions were nonsignificant using *t*-test.

On the other hand, computed percent WH differed significantly from actual reductions in yield. This means that farmers made good estimates of their expected yield losses due to SB. Actual percent damage, however, did not coincide with percent yield reduction, which disproved their statement that percent WH equals percent yield reduction.

About 70% of the farmers obtained yield losses greater than actual SB damage. The estimates they gave, however, were fairly close to percent yield loss they obtained. This means that factors other than WH caused greater yield reduction. Farmers attributed these differences to factors such as poor soil, lack of fertilizer, late planting, and unfavorable weather. Farmers need to pay more attention to these factors before worrying about SB. ■

Distribution of farmers' estimates of percent WH in Nueva Ecija, Philippines, 1992 WS.

Managing thrips in the Mekong Delta, Vietnam

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Thrips *Stenchaetothrips biformis* infestations in Vietnam usually occur about 10 d after sowing (DAS) and are highly visible. Farmers often react by spraying insecticides which can be detrimental to the rice crop by making it more susceptible to brown planthoppers.

We evaluated several thrips management tactics (see table) at the Dinh Thanh experimental station in An Giang

Province from Dec 1992 to Mar 1993. We used a randomized block design with four replications; plots were 4 × 4 m². Fertilizer was applied at 46 kg N/ha as urea and 40 kg P/ha as diammonium phosphate at 10 DAS, 46 kg N at 25 DAS, and 23 kg N at 45 DAS. Rice variety MTL 58 was seeded at 200 kg/ha.

Thrips infestations were assessed using three 20- × 20-cm² quadrats per plot. Percent rolled leaves at 1 and 2 wk after sowing (WAS) was not significantly different. At 3 WAS, percent rolled leaves was lowest in the BPMC-treated plots. Yields, however, were not significantly different across treatments (see table).